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MODERN METHODS OF DEVELOPING LISTENING AND READING SKILLS IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Abstract. This article analysis the advantages of using modern educational technologies, interactive methods, and digital resources in the formation and development of listening and reading skills in English lessons. It also provides examples of activities, innovative approaches, and pedagogical recommendations for the effective development of these skills. Active listening improves language skills through mental processing and accurate recording. It also helps to hear sounds, master vocabulary and grammar, and improve the accuracy of written speech.

Keywords: listening and reading skills, language learning, modern methods, materials, listening and reading exercises, linguistic difficulties

Аннотация. В данной статье освещаются преимущества использования современных образовательных технологий, интерактивных методов и цифровых ресурсов в формировании и развитии навыков аудирования и чтения на уроках английского языка. Также приводятся примеры заданий, инновационных подходов и педагогические рекомендации для эффективного развития этих навыков. Активное аудирования улучшает языковые навыки за счет умственной обработки и точной записи. Оно также помогает слышать звуки, осваивать лексику и грамматику, а также повышать точность письменной речи.

Ключевые слова: навыки аудирования и чтения, изучение языка, современные методы, материалы, упражнения на аудирование и чтение, языковые трудности

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz tili darslarida tinglab tushunish va o‘qish ko‘nikmalarini shakllantirish va rivojlantirishda zamonaviy ta’lim texnologiyalari, interaktiv metodlar hamda raqamli resurslardan foydalanishning afzalliklari yoritilgan. Shuningdek, ushbu ko‘nikmalarni samarali rivojlantirish uchun mo‘ljallangan mashg‘ulotlar namunasi, innovatsion yondashuvlar va pedagogik tavsiyalar keltirilgan. Faol tinglash, aqliy ishlov berish va aniq yozib olish orqali til ko‘nikmalarini yaxshilaydi. Shuningdek, u tovushlarni eshitish, lug‘at va grammatikani o‘zlashtirish, yozma nutq aniqligini oshirishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: tinglash va o‘qish ko‘nikmalari, til o‘rganish, zamonaviy usullar, materiallar, tinglash va o‘qish mashqlari, lingvistik qiyinchiliklar

Language is the main criterion of human communication, a set of sounds and words used to express various meanings and emotions. Studies in various areas of language show that learning a language is an extremely complex process, requiring the human mind to first listen, then express it as a dialogue, then further develop it through reading, and finally consolidate it in the form of a text. The development of technology, linguistics and pedagogy has created the basis for the further improvement of the processes of language teaching and learning. As humans constantly communicate with each other on a daily basis, they try to understand the speech of the other interlocutor through listening. Listening comprehension refers to listening, perceiving and understanding during vocal speech (speaking). In general, the term "speech" refers to speaking, listening comprehension, reading comprehension, and writing. In fact, it is more appropriate to say "listening and understanding of speaking." In the process of globalization, the role of English as an international language of communication is increasingly increasing. Therefore, the effective use of modern methodologies in its study and teaching is becoming increasingly important. In particular, listening comprehension and

reading skills are important components of communicative competence, which serve as the basis for understanding oral and written speech.

Extra linguistic difficulties include the environment of the listening process, the number of students participating in the lesson, the quality of audio materials, the speed or slowness of speech, speech intonation, sound timbres, the intelligibility of the task being performed, etc. Linguistic difficulties, in turn, are related to the grammatical aspects of the language. Examples of these include phonetic (distinguishing sounds), morphological (inability to analyze the formation of words), syntactic (using words correctly, connecting them) and other difficulties. Psychological difficulties are related to the psyche of the learner. For example, the child's character type is an example of this. Some children prefer to see or touch rather than hear, and this is precisely why they hinder the development of listening comprehension competence.

There are some methods for developing listening comprehension:

Listening comprehension is a key skill that should be developed from the very beginning of language learning. The following methods serve this purpose:

- Podcasts and audiobooks: Audio materials develop listeners' phonetic, intonation, and lexical knowledge.

- Interactive applications (e.g. Duolingo, BBC Learning English): Students can complete independent listening exercises.

Duo lingo is a language-learning website and mobile app where users learn using “networks” tailored to their target language, with specific “skills” to practice vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation through spaced repetition. Skills-based exercises can include written translation, reading comprehension, speaking comprehension, and short story exercises.

Authentic materials: Practical language skills are developed through audio files based on real-life conversations.

Audiovisual media: Multimodal learning is developed through films, series, and documentary videos. For example, listening with subtitles simultaneously activates the student's visual and auditory channels.

Now we will discuss methods for developing reading skills;

Reading serves to increase vocabulary, understand grammatical structure, and develop logical thinking in the process of language learning. The following methods are effective:

Skimming and scanning techniques improve the ability to quickly identify the main idea or find the necessary information. E-books and online articles help to develop a wide range of learning activities are carried out through texts of various genres. Discussion-based reading is students' thinking and argumentative skills based on the text they read are developed.

As an important source, the book “Methods of working with texts in the English language” by R. Mahmudov extensively analyzes reading strategies and methods. It is noted that with the help of these strategies, students can develop the skills of quickly finding information in complex texts, distinguishing the main idea and summarizing the content. Interactive methods in teaching English, unlike traditional teaching models, are aimed at involving the student in the learning process as an active participant. This is an important factor in the formation and strengthening of reading skills. The use of interactive technologies (cluster, “Insert”, “Brainstorming”, “Venn diagram”, role-playing games, etc.) in the educational process increases the ability of students to work independently with the text, think, distinguish the main idea and draw conclusions. Conscious reading of texts in the English language activates not only the student's lexical and grammatical knowledge, but also cognitive activities such as analysis, comparison, and generalization. This is consistent with competency-based models of education.

Interactive methods form the ability of students to use the language, not just to know it. Also, in the process of learning to read in English, students need to acquire not only lexical and syntactic knowledge, but also the ability to motivate, reason, and understand the structure of the text. In addition, the results obtained in groups taught using interactive methods were higher than in traditional classes.

The formation of listening comprehension and reading skills in English lessons is an important factor in students' active language acquisition. The use of modern technologies, interactive methods, and authentic materials in the development of these skills increases the effectiveness of the lesson. Understanding what they hear through audio and visual means, as well as analyzing texts based on digital resources, encourages students to think independently. Organizing lessons based on communicative and differentiated approaches ensures an approach appropriate to the level of knowledge of students. Therefore, teachers should thoroughly study innovative methodologies and effectively apply them in practice. This will bring the quality of English teaching to a new level.

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